

Review of experimental studies in allergy:

1) Clinical studies

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Abstract

The incidence of allergic conditions is increasing. The treatment of allergic conditions by homoeopathy is one of the most extensively investigated aspects of clinical homoeopathy. The author reviews the use of isotherapy and other homoeopathic therapeutic strategies in homoeopathy. Open studies of homoeopathic treatment of allergic conjunctivitis, rhinitis, asthma and sensitivity to Cotrimoxazole are discussed. Controlled clinical trials of Galphimia glanca in hayfever and specific isotherapy in hayfever and asthma are discussed and criticised.

KEYWORDS: Allergy; Isotherapy; Desensitization; Specific immunotherapy; Open studies; Controlled studies.

Introduction

Allergology is currently expanding substantially, due to the growing incidence of allergic pathology in developed countries (15 million people are affected in France¹) and the very rapid progress made in practical and basic immunoallergology. While the place of classical therapies is thus increasingly well codified, that of unconventional or 'alternative' treatments remains immensely controversial.

Jacques Charpin,² on the subject of atypical treatments for asthma, pointed out that doctors' advice is often sought by patients about a number of methods which do not fall within classic therapy. It is impossible to have an opinion about homoeopathy of which some of our patients sometimes report favourable experience, as there has been no controlled French study in this field. It would, however, be desirable for such a study to appear as a result of honest co-operation between a first-class homoeopath and a competent asthmology department.

More recently, two French chest specialists³ writing about a publication in the *Lancet* relating to the action of very highly diluted allergens in the treatment of asthma (see below), noted

that 'homoeopathy turned out to be more effective than the placebo, which is disturbing' and stress 'the need for further work including a larger number of patients before considering, in the case of asthmatics showing a tendency towards improved respiratory function, combining the usual therapies with homoeopathic immunotherapy which, if it can do no harm, could perhaps do some good...'

Subsequently, Leynadier⁴ has referred to the placebo effect: 'Recently, a journal made an inventory of all "alternative" therapies used to treat allergic complaints. Virtually none have given objective proof of efficacy when subjected to scientific methodology, i.e. a placebo-controlled double blind trial.'

Finally, very recently, Molina⁵ summed up his opinion of this therapy as follows: 'some doctors have published studies which tend to prove success in pollenosis. Basophil degranulation by very dilute antiserum against IgE has given rise to very great controversy in France. In fact, no clinical study has given convincing results and, in particular, has been unable to explain the mechanism of any efficacy such treatments might have. More than this, comparison with the use of low doses of allergenic

extracts has caused some confusion in people's minds and has been one of the reasons for loss of interest in and criticism of immunotherapy.⁷

These four points of view seem quite representative of what has happened when French allergologists have looked at homoeopathy.

From the point of view of doctors who use homoeopathic medicines, several factors argue in favour of a real place for homoeopathy in treating allergic illnesses:

- *Reasons for homoeopathic consultation*, amongst which allergic pathology looms large, for instance in the US, allergic rhinitis is the leading reason for consulting a homoeopathic doctor.⁶
- *The content of the homoeopathic materia medica*, where the semiology of many remedies refers to allergic and inflammatory reactions, as well as to the 'diathesis' of allergic patients.
- *Clinical and biological research work*, some of which points to the efficacy of homoeopathically prepared medicines in treating allergic illnesses.
- *The practical approach to allergic illnesses*, these are mediated by immunological mechanisms triggered by environmental factors, not only specific allergens, but also predisposing factors. In allergology, the triggering circumstances and specific symptomatology, as well as the susceptibility of the atopic patient in particular, occupy an important place. Moreover, these illnesses often involve a change in the state of health in the long term, which needs to be treated with the least aggressive therapy available.

Within this clinical picture, homoeopathic treatment, prescribed on the basis of symptomatology, aetiological circumstances and diathesis, is one of the therapeutic responses which should be explored in treating allergic diseases and improving the health of these patients.

The review of literature on the role of alternative medicine in the treatment of allergic illnesses carried out by Watkins⁷ examines two general reviews, four clinical trials, one biological study and two clinical case studies in 'homoeopathy'. The experimental study of homoeopathy in allergic illnesses or through biological tests used in allergology,⁸ covers a much broader range of publications.

We shall describe the majority of studies effected, distinguishing:

- those which are preliminary or rely on inadequate methodology and whose improvement might lead to further work.
- those relying on more rigorous methodology which will be analysed in detail.

The results of clinical trials will be studied, biological results and data relating to the mechanisms involved being considered in a second section.

Before examining scientific publications dealing with the action of highly dilute substances in clinical and basic allergology, it is worthwhile mentioning a particular use of these high dilution - highly dilute allergens - in treating allergic illnesses.

Desensitization or specific immunotherapy

The confusion noted by Molina⁵ with regard to the comparison between specific immunotherapy and the use of low doses of allergenic extracts, can prove quite real if one considers, for example, that in a recent trial of 30c dilutions of allergens in asthma, the therapeutic method used was described as 'oral homoeopathic immunotherapy'. It is therefore necessary to define these two therapeutic strategies carefully.⁹

Desensitization consists of administering to an allergic patient, by subcutaneous injection, progressively increasing doses of the allergen to which the patient is sensitive, to reduce the harmful effects of contact with the allergen (rhinitis, conjunctivitis and asthma). Originally empirical, this method is now much better defined, its effectiveness has been demonstrated in allergy to bee and wasp stings and in asthma caused by acarids and pollens, as well as in rhinitis caused by acarids and pollen, provided that the benefits and risks of this treatment in comparison with the effectiveness of drug treatment have been properly assessed.¹⁰ Indications extend to animal (cat) protein and moulds (*alternaria*). Administration does not have to be subcutaneous: recent works on desensitization by sublingual administration in treating pollenosis, show that this method has a real effect and seems to be risk free.¹¹

For a long time, the mechanism was believed to be variations in the IgE and IgC levels, the latter being antibodies blocking the IgE receptor sites on cells possessing high affinity receptors (basophils and mast cells). Other mechanisms have been demonstrated more recently: inhibition of the delayed reaction

dependent on the IgE antibodies and reduction of reactivity to the allergen of the target organs and inflammatory cells. Study of helper T lymphocyte sub-populations has shown the existence of a switch from T2 lymphocytes to T1 and T0, thus stressing the role of the T epitopes.¹² The T epitopes, peptides recognized by the T receptor in association with the class II molecules of the major histocompatibility complex, are involved in the phenomenon of antigen presentation, in competition between peptides for this presentation in lymphocyte proliferation, as well as in the nature of that proliferation (T1 versus T2). Work in this field has shown great variation in epitope recognition 'between and within patients, which leads Tunon de Lara¹³ to say that 'It is not therefore certain that a reductionist approach to the epitopes involved in allergic mechanisms could resolve a set of problems characterized by diversity and individual susceptibility'. However, inducing tolerance by means of T epitopes is still an interesting line of research, as these epitopes do not usually have the ability to bind to IgE, which could reduce the undesirable effects in comparison with native allergens.

To sum up, while the technique of specific immunotherapy is moving forward as a result of the standardization of allergens, controlled trials and basic research, it still has its limits: possible systemic adverse reactions, cost compliance and treatment duration.

Use of highly dilute allergens in homoeopathy or isotherapy

Specific isopathy means the use of high dilutions of the allergen(s) to which the patient is sensitive. It is rarely prescribed by homoeopaths in the first instance, but usually following the failure or insufficient action of other treatment. This prescribing technique, which should probably be more precisely called specific isotherapy is still empirical. Depending on their experience, practitioners use varying frequencies of administration and dosages.^{14,15}

- Most often, dilutions on a rising scale from 5-30c in the first six months, followed by administration twice and then once a month of 30c doses for two or three years.
- More rarely, a descending scale of dilution, closer to desensitization techniques.
- Sometimes staggered doses of 15 and 30 potency.

Administration protocols are often adapted to the reactivity of patients. To date, there has been no validation of different homoeopathic immunotherapy protocols for long-term treatment (Reilly's studies on the effect of isopathy at 30c potency refer to monitoring hay fever or allergic asthma attacks over a short period).

The differences between specific immunotherapy and specific isotherapy are therefore important. Even though many homoeopaths use the same term, desensitization, to describe such use of highly dilute allergens, the existence of such differences and the lack of understanding of the biological action mechanisms of highly dilute allergens does not currently, pending experimental and clinical studies, allow this method to be put on the same footing as classic desensitization.

In the same way, the term 'non-specific desensitization' is often used by homoeopaths to describe the expected effects of prescribing dilutions of *Histaminum* and *Lung histamine* (a product prepared following anaphylactic shock in guinea pigs and containing many mediators of immediate allergic reaction). This expression actually covers the ability, suggested by clinical observation and in-vitro work on the activation of basophils, that these two medicines might regulate the effects of allergic mediators, a point considered in more depth later when describing research work and clinical practice.

Clinical trials

In order to get a better understanding of the subject, we shall briefly describe the broad lines of homoeopathic practice in allergology, inasmuch as they influence the methodology of the clinical trials and the interpretation of their results. While aware that only the results of controlled trials comparing homoeopathic remedies with placebos and standard treatment can be conclusive, we shall briefly mention the results of three open studies and three uncontrolled comparative trials as they illustrate the reality of homoeopathic practice and could provide a basis for controlled trials. I will then describe the results of controlled trials, making a critique in comparison with classic methodology.

Therapeutic strategy in homoeopathy and the notion of individualization

While clinical observation is the foundation of homoeopathy, it no longer suffices to demon-

strate its efficacy, for reasons which are not specific to homoeopathy: spontaneous progress of disease and the placebo effect common to all therapies. Demonstrations of the efficacy of homoeopathy can only rely today on controlled double-blind trials with placebos or standard treatments.¹⁶ However, these trials must also incorporate the characteristics of the homoeopathic method. In broad outline, this is characterized by individualized prescription on the basis of 1, the 'clinical form' of the illness and 2, the characteristics of the patient, his/her personal and family background and reactions to the environment, his/her susceptibility in terms of reaction.

There are several homoeopathic prescription techniques. The so-called 'unicist' approach involves prescribing a single drug likely to cover the whole clinical picture. Other practitioners in France¹⁷ and other countries^{18,19} mostly use the so-called 'pluralist' approach, which incorporates nosological diagnosis in its approach. The results of a survey of practice related to the therapeutic approach of homoeopathic doctors in pollenosis provide a concrete illustration of the use of this technique in treating allergic illnesses.

Homoeopaths practising the pluralist approach, use the following²⁰ in order of frequency:

- Symptomatic drugs, the most commonly prescribed being, in order of frequency, *Apis mellifica*, *Allium cepa*, *Sabadilla* and *Euphrasia*.
- Basic medicines intended to treat the diathesis: *Psorinum*, *Sulturnum*, *Natrum muriaticum*, *Thuja*, *Lycopodium* and *Arsenicum album* are the most commonly prescribed.
- Dilutions of biological allergic mediators, especially *Lung histamine*.
- Isopathy, less commonly used.

While this therapeutic strategy cannot be standardized, it does lend itself to individualized assessment, since 13 basic remedies (92% of cases), 13 acute remedies (87% of cases) and dilutions of *Lung histamine* (67% of cases) and pollens (62% of cases) account for the bulk of prescriptions. These could be assessed on the basis of controlled trials in relation to placebos or standard treatment, but are still individualized treatments which must be prescribed by homoeopathic doctors. In view of the practical

difficulties raised by the organization of such trials, controlled trials conducted in homoeopathy have avoided the problem of individualization by assessing the effectiveness of an isolated symptomatic or isopathic treatment.

Broadly speaking, the therapeutic strategy used in pollenosis can be applied to other allergic ENT, lung (asthma) or skin^{14,21} pathology. Homoeopathic therapy, alone or as a complement to allopathic therapy, is set up according to a therapeutic register which takes into account the various factors of allergic illness: 1, Allergens and the environment; 2, The mechanisms of allergic reaction; 3, The reactivity of the target organ(s); 4, The diathesis of the allergic patient; and 5, Psychosomatic factors.

In asthma, a more complex pathology in which the allergic factor is rarely isolated, the practitioner must simultaneously treat inflammation and bronchospasm and alter the allergic diathesis, while assessing the role of environmental factors, from tobacco to the various industrial pollutants, climatic, infectious and affective factors and those relating to the autonomic nervous system. The use of homoeopathy alone is often insufficient, especially at the beginning of treatment, and must take into account any [medical] consensus reached. The homoeopathic doctor thus acts on the basis of sound knowledge of semiology, homoeopathic therapy and classic pharmacology.

Open trials

We shall describe here trials conducted on 1, allergic conjunctivitis: in a multicentre study exploring individualized homoeopathic treatment; 2, allergic rhinitis: treated by a combination of three remedies, *Apis mellifica* 15cH, *Pollen 30cH* and *Lung histamine* 15cH and 3, preventing skin reactions to cotrimoxazole (Trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole) in patients carrying the AIDS virus, by means of 9c and 15c dilutions of TMP-SMX.

Multicentre study of allergic conjunctivitis

Although the methodology is not insufficiently rigorous, this study does explore the reality of homoeopathic practice. Conducted by members of the French society of homoeopathic ophthalmology,²² it covered 72 cases of allergic conjunctivitis, associated with blepharitis in 27 cases and with other allergic symptoms in 40% of cases. Skin tests were conducted on 43 cases and were positive, mainly to house dust

mite, moulds and acarids. No measurement of IgE levels or RASTs were requested. Homoeopathic treatment included symptomatic and diathetic medicines, medicines prescribed on the basis of physical pathology and isopathic medicines. Duration of treatment was from 3–12 months. The results were assessed in accordance with functional and objective signs.

Of the 72 cases, five showed no improvement, seven had slight improvement in functional signs, 20 a clear improvement and 40 an improvement in subjective and objective signs without relapse. In their conclusion, the authors note the weakness of their study, especially with regard to allergological appraisal and the need for monitoring over a longer period. A controlled study needs to be conducted to confirm the results of this preliminary study.

Action of a homoeopathic compound in pollenosis

This multicentre study conducted in Belgium²³ observed the effect of a homoeopathic compound combining *Apis mellifica* 15cH, Lung histamine 15cH and Pollen 30cH (prepared from a mixture of 12 grass pollens). The regime was one tablet per day for six months. Of the 108 observations, 73 patients received this treatment alone, 35 patients also received symptomatic and prophylactic treatment. Progress was monitored by noting the score of nasal symptoms (rhinorrhoea, obstruction, sneezing and pruritus) and ocular symptoms (sneezing and watering), as well as the basis of an assessment by the treating doctor. The percentage of patients showing improvement varied according to symptoms, from 69%–86% for patients taking the compound alone and 82%–91% for the group also receiving symptomatic treatment. A controlled trial is to be conducted.

Action of dilute cotrimoxazole on HIV-positive patients sensitive to the drug

20 HIV-positive patients with skin reactions (maculo-papulous rash) to cotrimoxazole, received isotherapy with this drug at a potency of 9cH for ten days and a potency of 15cH for the next ten days.²⁴ The patients then resumed prophylactic cotrimoxazole in substantial doses, the average follow-up was six months. In 13 patients, there was no recurrence of the skin reaction on resuming cotrimoxazole. The seven other patients had a skin reaction, in the

next 24 hours in six cases and after three months in the other. No undesirable effects occurred during administration of the 9cH and 15cH isopathic dilutions. According to the authors, the results of this study should be confirmed by a controlled double-blind trial.

Uncontrolled comparative trials

Three studies will be described here, one compared the action of desensitization to that of isotherapy, the other two assessed the action of two homoeopathic remedies in asthma.

Comparative study between desensitization and isotherapy

This was a retrospective study carried out by a pneumologist and allergologist who, after long practising classic desensitization, introduced homoeopathy into his therapeutics, using diathetic treatment and isotherapy.²⁵ This was a comparative study without randomization or blinding, in which the patients were free to choose between classic desensitization by injection or mouth and isotherapy. It covered 66 patients, 21 suffering from pollenosis and 45 suffering from allergic asthma in reaction to acarids, house dust or moulds. Desensitization was practised in the traditional way with slow-release extracts. Isotherapy consisted of 5 granules of the 5cH daily for the first month, 7cH the second month and then 9c, 12c, 15c, 24c and 30c up to the seventh month. The treatment was then extended by doses twice and once a month for asthma caused by acarids and moulds. For pollens, the author used a 15c dilution prescribed on a weekly or twice weekly basis during the pollen season. Observation was concerned with:

- possible adverse reactions: there were more of these with traditional desensitization than isotherapy. Two reactions were nevertheless observed with isotherapy, one with the pollen dilutions and the other with acarid dilutions.
- improvement as assessed by the doctor: of the 45 asthmatic patients, results were positive or very positive in 58% of cases with isotherapy and 61% with traditional desensitization. In both groups, the failure rate was around 15%. Amongst the 22 patients suffering from pollenosis, there was improvement in 63% of cases with isotherapy and 61% with desensitization. The failure rate was 20% in both groups.

The author concludes by observing that both methods gave similar results but isotherapy was better tolerated, and advocates that a multi-centre study be carried out.

Lung histamine in asthma

This study, conducted by the homoeopathy department of the Federal University of Rio Grande de Norte (Brazil), concerned the action of Lung histamine 5c in the prophylaxis of asthma in children aged 2–6 years.²⁶ The assessment criterion was the frequency of attacks in the three months prior to taking the remedy and the three months afterwards. Ninety children were monitored in this way and the results compared with those of an untreated group of children over the same period. The monthly average was 1.69 attacks before treatment in the first group and 0.38 afterwards. In the second group, it was 1.68 and 1.54, respectively. The difference was highly significant for the first group before and after treatment, and insignificant for the second group. The inadequacies of this trial are stressed by the authors. Inadequate allergological diagnosis and the disparity of the groups make a new study necessary.

Blatta orientalis in asthma

During a study conducted at the paediatric department of Sao Paulo Hospital (Brazil), *Blatta orientalis* (cockroach) at 2x and 3x potency considerably reduced the frequency of asthma attacks in children.²⁷ However, when the same team repeated the trial, as part of a placebo-controlled study, the efficacy observed for *Blatta orientalis* 6cH was not different from the placebo.²⁸

This last point suggests that while patients may show a substantial improvement in these uncontrolled trials, it is nevertheless difficult to separate the specific effect of the remedy from the relationship between doctor and patient or changes in the patient's environment advised at the time of the consultation.

Controlled clinical trials

Controlled clinical trials of homoeopathy were the subject of a review covering 107 trials.²⁹ Of the 22 trials which obtained a satisfactory grading from the authors (>55/100), five involved the treatment of hay fever, either with high dilutions of pollen, or with a homoeopathic preparation, *Galphimia glauca*. Two other

trials conducted in allergology were classed amongst those whose methodology was not sufficiently rigorous.

Effect of Galphimia glauca in pollenosis

Galphimia glauca is a remedy prepared from a Mexican plant in regular use in Germany. In the first trial, the effect of *Galphimia glauca* 4x was compared to that of the placebo, assessment being based on the score of symptoms.³⁰ In the two groups, of 41 and 45 patients, respectively, the score improved by 47% in week 2 and 57% in week 4 in the placebo group, as against 83% and 81%, respectively, in the other. The difference is statistically significant.

In the second trial, in which the effect of *Galphimia* 6x was compared to the placebo and an unshaken dilution, there was a statistically significant difference for the 6x group in the score of symptoms in the second week (60% as against 40% and 41% in the other two groups), but not in the fourth week.³¹ In a third trial, the 2c, 4c, 4x and 4LM dilutions gave comparable improvements in scores in the second (64%, 73%, 65% and 76%, respectively) and fourth (83%, 79%, 82% and 85%, respectively) weeks.³²

Although the methodology of these trials was rigorous, it is not clear why the authors changed the dilutions studied.

Effect of high isopathic dilutions in hay fever and asthma

Principle

These trials referring to isotherapy do not constitute an evaluation of homoeopathic therapy. Isopathy is only part of homoeopathic treatment. On its own, it may be less effective than an overall treatment, adapted not only to the causal agent, but also to the clinical form of the illness and the characteristics of the patient. The study of isotherapy does, however, offer a simple model for comparing the action of a high dilution with that of a placebo, which was the main purpose of the studies described below. In addition, such studies might lead to comparative trials between traditional desensitization and isotherapy.

Controlled trial of a homoeopathic dilution of Pollen 30c in hay fever as a model.

The study on high dilutions (30c) of Pollen³³ got the best score in the systematic review, the

reservations referred only to the fact that the number of patients per group was under 100.²⁹ In this study, the question was whether there was a placebo effect in high dilutions containing no further traces of the active principle and not related to the efficacy of homoeopathy. The chosen model, the action of *Pollen 30c* in hay fever comes directly from the work of Blackley, who was already a homoeopathic doctor when, between 1871 and 1873, he identified pollen as the cause of hay fever.³⁴ Reilly *et al.* also pointed out that homoeopaths were using high dilutions of pollen at least 20 years before Noon introduced injections of allergens for prophylactic purposes in 1911. We are therefore clearly dealing with an evaluation of isotherapy, used as a model for testing the clinical efficacy of high dilutions and not an evaluation of homoeopathy.

This was a double-blind placebo-controlled of mixed *Pollen 30c* on 158 patients who had been suffering from seasonal rhinitis as a result of pollen allergy for at least two years. The diagnosis was confirmed in 112 of the patients by skin tests and/or level of total and specific IgE antibodies. The majority of cases involved a single sensitivity: of the 96 patients who had a RAST, only 12 showed allergy to antigens other than pollen.

1) *Selection.* Patients were excluded if they were: displaying only ocular signs, suffering from asthma or infection, pregnant or lactating women and patients suffering serious pathology. Patients had to have stopped taking any antihistamines, drugs such as sodium cromoglycate or inhaled corticosteroids for 24 hours, corticosteroids by mouth for a week and slow-release corticosteroids for eight weeks. Selection was carried out by 26 NHS doctors at the Glasgow and Royal London Homoeopathic Hospitals.

2) *Treatment.* After inclusion and randomization, patients received placebo for a week and then, for two weeks, two daily doses of a tablet impregnated with a dilution of the pollen mixture at a potency of 30c, or a tablet impregnated with the alcohol-water solution used to prepare the pollen dilutions (placebo). During the following two weeks, treatment was stopped, while patients continued to note their symptoms. In the event of substantial clinical symptoms, the patients had access to antihistamines at a rate of 1-3 chlorpheniramine 4 mg tablets per day.

3) *The main assessment criterion.* This was a 100 mm analogue visual scale on which patients noted their symptoms each day. This method proved to be sensitive, a difference of 5% between the two groups having clinical relevance. The average progress of this criterion in the two groups was analysed by analysis of covariance. The average weekly pollen count was taken into consideration in the statistical analysis.

4) *Results.* Of the 158 patients included, five were lost to follow up (1 isotherapy (I), 4 placebo (P)), 9 monitored by postal questionnaire (4 I, 5 P), 17 left the trial (9 I, 8 P) and 19 violated the protocol (9 I, 10 P). Full data were obtained on 108 patients (56 I, 52 P). At the end of the four weeks, the group receiving *Pollen 30c* showed an average reduction on the analogue visual scale of 17.2 mm (SD 28.8) as against 2.6 mm (SD 33.6) for the placebo group. The difference was significant ($p=0.02$), as it was for the assessment made by the doctors. Statistical analysis showed that the difference could not be due to fluctuations in the pollen count, the difference becoming even more significant ($p=0.01$) when this parameter was taken into account. Furthermore, the number of cases of aggravation during the first week was significantly greater ($p < 0.05$) in the *Pollen* group (21) in comparison with the placebo group (11). The total number of antihistamine tablets taken during the trial was also significantly lower ($p=0.003$) in the *Pollen* group (11.2, SD 13.5) compared to the placebo group (19.7, SD 18.6), consumption had been identical before the start of the trial. Statistical analysis confirmed that the improvement in the pollen group was not due to a low number of patients taking a large amount of antihistamines. The results of this study thus confirm those of the pilot study.³⁵

5) *Critique of the trial.* The main remark concerns the number (33%) of subjects excluded from the analysis.³⁶ However, the distribution of those leaving the trial or violating the protocol is the same in both groups. The other remark relates to the choice of isotherapy. This is a wise choice in carrying out a clinical trial, as it gets around the problem of individualization, but it does not explore the prescribing method of homoeopathic remedies. However, the use of isotherapy allows one of the foundation of

homoeopathic therapeutics to be examined, i.e. the action of high dilutions on a sensitive patient, even though the similarity of reaction is not incorporated in the approach. In this case, we have sensitized subjects within the known biological framework of immediate hypersensitivity. The period of aggravation which followed the administration of the treatment well illustrates what practitioners observe when administering 'diathetic' remedies, i.e. an increase in reactivity when high dilutions are taken by a 'sensitive' subject. We should point out, moreover, that we are dealing with a particular use of isotherapy (*Pollen 30c* being prescribed during the pollen season), whereas it is commonly used prior to the season. The authors in fact favoured pre-season treatment, in order to reduce the aggravation observed at the beginning of the treatment. Of course, this study needs to be repeated by another team. It was not until eight years later that the same team published a study in the same journal, also dealing with isotherapy, although the pathology (allergic asthma) was different.

Effect of 30c potency isotherapy in allergic asthma.

This was a double-blind placebo-controlled randomized study with two parallel groups. The authors' objective was to answer the question 'is homoeopathy a placebo response?' by confirming the results of the trial on pollenosis, which highlighted a significant difference between *Pollen 30c* and the placebo. With this in mind, they conducted a study on allergic asthma.³⁷

1) *Selection.* Patients (an expected number of 60 in each group) were selected from the beginning of February, before the pollen season in Scotland. Patients were seen by a respiratory physician and a homoeopathic doctor. They had to present with asthma progressing for more than one year with sensitivity to lung allergens. Skin tests were conducted, as were respiratory function tests (forced expiratory volume for the first second – FEV₁ and vital capacity), while bronchial reactivity to histamine was measured. The hospital pharmacist noted treatments taken orally or inhaled. In this trial which was double-blind, patients received a dose of placebo and were monitored for four weeks to

ensure that their symptoms were stable. A case conference was held to confirm inclusion and to determine the main allergen with a view to desensitization. The selected patients were then randomized and stratification was implemented according to allergen and daily dose of inhaled steroids (none; <1000 µg; >1000 µg).

2) *Treatment.* The patients then received the treatment consisting either of a 30c dilution of the allergen to which they were sensitive (skin tests and case history), or a placebo consisting of globules impregnated with the solvent which had been diluted and shaken in the same way ('potentised'). The isopathic remedies were prepared from allergens supplied by the Pasteur Institute, dilution being carried out by a French homoeopathic laboratory in accordance with the rules of the French pharmacopoeia. The presence of contaminants (corticosteroids, theophylline or other) was measured on randomly selected samples. In 23 cases out of 28, the allergens responsible were acarids, the five other allergens being cats, dogs, moulds and feathers. Treatment was given in the form of three doses taken over 24 hours. The remedies were administered directly by the hospital pharmacist.

3) *Criteria for assessment.* The patients noted their symptoms in a daily diary for four weeks, their overall progress being monitored using a visual analogue scale (VAS) ranging from 0 to 100 mm. Patients were seen again four weeks later for a clinical and respiratory check-up, having freely continued their previous treatment. The main outcome criterion was symptom severity measured by VAS. It had been intended to enter 60 patients in each group with an expected difference of 15 mm on the VAS, a significance threshold of 5% and a power of 80%, but only 28 patients were included, as selection was halted before the pollen season. Statistical analysis was carried out.

4) *Results.* Of the 28 patients included, four left the trial, two in each group. Of the 24 patients in whom changes were compared to the initial values over a period of four weeks after randomization, progress on the VAS reflected a difference in favour of the isotherapy group after the first week, which became greater over the next two weeks and was maintained subsequently, both curves levelling off. At the end of the fourth week, the patients receiving the placebo (P) had got worse on average (5 out of 13 were improved), while the patients receiving

ing the 30c dilutions of the allergen (group I) showed clear improvement on average (9 patients out of 11 showing improvement). The average reduction on the VAS was 7.2 (Standard Error of Mean (SEM) 3.2) for the active group, while the placebo group showed a rise of 7.8 (SEM 3.0), ($p = 0.003$, 95% confidence interval (-24.1 to 5.9)). The difference between the two groups exceeded 33%, a difference between groups of over 30% on the scale being considered clinically relevant in asthma. The clinical assessment given by patients (recorded by the chest physician) and by the homoeopathic doctor, was also in favour of the homoeopathy group. Of the objective criteria measured, the results of the respiratory function tests (measurement of vital capacity and forced expiratory volume for the first second) and bronchial reactivity to histamine (PC 20) favoured the group treated with homoeopathy which showed an improvement of respiratory function (FEV₁: +3%) and a reduction in bronchial reactivity to histamine, the contrary being observed in the control group (FEV₁: -7%). The trend in favour of homoeopathy is reflected in a statistically significant difference as regards vital capacity (FVC +0.07 l in the active, -0.33 l in the placebo group, $p = 0.03$). Only 18 patients were able to undergo these tests, 3 patients from each group being unable to undertake them at the end of the trial.

5) *Criticism.* This study was controversial in several respects:

- Low number of subjects. While it is true that obtaining a significant difference with a small number of subjects in each group argues in favour of great efficacy of treatment, it would have been desirable to include the planned number of subjects, in order to determine whether a significant difference also existed on the respiratory function tests. The authors were unable to recruit a sufficient number, but this aspect could be improved in a subsequent trial.
- Failure to monitor the traditional treatment of asthma during the trial. In the article, the authors mention that patients were asked not to change their treatment and that they complied, except for one patient receiving the placebo who took oral corticosteroids for the last two weeks. In fact, the use of bronchodilator drugs was the same in both groups, although the relevant table was not published.³⁸

- The choice of the VAS as the main criterion, despite there being no significant difference on the FEV₁. A new study involving a larger number of subjects might provide a response on these objective parameters.
- Statistical criticisms too detailed to be discussed here. As the authors of a critical article³⁹ rightly pointed out: 'the methodology of the trial was generally acceptable. In other words, if a non-homoeopathic treatment had been involved, no-one would have thought to challenge the trial'.
- Criticisms regarding non-observance of blind trial principles.⁵ The personal involvement of Reilly⁴⁰ and the role of the laboratory manufacturing the product, are harder to accept. Of the eight authors of the article, six are members of Glasgow University, who are entirely neutral with regard to homoeopathy. Their signature and the *Lancet* agreement to publish, bear witness to the integrity of the approach, should this be necessary.

In my opinion, the two most important criticisms concern the number of subjects which was too small for the objective parameters studied (lack of power) and the precise recording of treatment followed before and during the trial by the patients.

Meta-analysis of the three studies.

The two trials on pollenosis and this trial on asthma had three points in common: respiratory allergy allergens, treatment with 'homoeopathic immunotherapy' (I prefer the term specific isotherapy) in the form of a 30c dilution of allergen and the use of a VAS to assess progress. On this basis, the authors carried out a meta-analysis to answer the question whether studies showing that the action of homoeopathy is different from that of the placebo can be replicated. The average of daily differences in relation to the baseline of the VAS, measured over the last two weeks of each trial, shows a statistically significant difference for the trials on pollenosis ($p = 0.02$ for the pilot trial and $p = 0.01$ for the main trial) and the trial on allergic asthma ($p = 0.003$). The overall statistical analysis covering 202 patients showed a highly significant difference ($p = 0.0004$).

Criticism.

The problem raised by this meta-analysis is that it was carried out on the basis of trials in

somewhat different pathologies. Even though the traditional purpose of meta-analyses is to improve therapeutic information, this one was not designed to answer the question raised by the therapeutic efficacy of isotherapy, but to assess the effect of high dilutions in comparison with a placebo. According to the authors, 'although the results could suggest that homoeopathic immunotherapy has a role to play in the treatment of these diseases, with reduced need for antihistamines in patients suffering from pollenosis and a trend towards improvement of respiratory function in patients suffering from asthma, we think that it is premature to speculate. The debate must focus on the challenge posed by the fact that patients repeatedly detect a greater effect from the homoeopathic medicine than from the placebo'. This leads the same authors to debate the 'implausibility' of the clinical action of high dilutions.

This point was picked up in the *Lancet* editorial, which only allowed for two possibilities: either 'something is wrong' with traditional clinical trials, or homoeopathic immunotherapy does not have the same effect as a placebo. These two hypotheses seemed equally absurd to the leader writer.⁴¹ In their discussion, Reilly and his colleagues leave the door open to the work of physicists 'more comfortable with such ideas than pharmacologists'. Mentioning the various hypotheses, they stress the interest of the new research field opened up by recent studies of high dilutions in nuclear magnetic resonance,⁴² a subject related to the study of how they actually work.

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